

How the synthetic Covid virus confirms God's creation of man.

For centuries, but ever since Darwin's origin of species, science has been opposed to religion, which proposes the creation of species as part of divine creation. This conflict between religion and science affects the human progress in the same way as the perspective on science and religion.

In the 21st century, the barrier between science and religion is unintentionally resolved by man.

A virus that has been carefully constructed from many genetic fragments becomes the focus of a society that enslaves itself through political and economic measures to the man-made virus and moves backwards in social development.

This virus, called the Covid-19 virus, was made from human and animal genetic fragments. It is the

highest development that humans has ever made.

The creation of an artificial genome from human-animal recombination to be injected into the human body to alter, and manipulate the human genome.

The scientists not only wanted to create artificial life, but also to change human creation itself. If this process were successful, Darwin would be right with his theory of the origin of species. Thus, synthetic creation and integration of foreign species into the human genome, could develop new or modified human species by inheritance of artificial genome to next generations.

If this theory were correct, then the new mRNA vaccinations would be successful. The injected artificial RNA would be integrated into the human genome and the information on the RNA would be translated for the protein synthesis. But the failure of the RNA vaccines and the allergic triggered

autoimmune reaction resulting in death speaks against this theory.

Breaking the barrier between humans and animals by crossing artificial human-animal genomes triggers an alert mechanism to protect the unique human genome. Mixing of human genome with animal or synthetic recombinations is prevented by exodus of humans.

The man-made Covid-19 virus is the scientific proof, that humans were created in his uniqueness by God to obtain inimitability at any price. While the creation of new species and variation of species through natural selection and cross transmission is feasible, this cannot happen with humans, because humans were created by God.

Darwin is right that species can change and develop through variation, but with regard to

humans, the development of the Homo Sapiens shows variation of the already existing human Neanderthal. Man changed through natural selection to today's modern man according to Darwin, but he was already created as man by God.

Science, therefore, completes and confirms the history of human creation and does not in anyway contradict it. Both God's creation and natural selection explain hand-in hand the human origin and the history of our planet.

In contrast, the synthetic human-animal recombinant genome was not created under natural selection pressure or was even part of a divine creation plan. Man violated all rules of natural and spiritual creation. And it is man who created the conflict between religion and science, while God is in harmony with nature.